

The Spanish press as an object of study for Communication researchers

La prensa española como objeto de estudio para los investigadores en Comunicación

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ABSTRACT

The Spanish press was the subject of numerous scientific studies in recent years. But what does the scientific community understand by the Spanish press? The main objective of this study is to conduct a detailed analysis of how the research community in the field of Communication has defined the notion of "the Spanish press" in the scientific literature. For this purpose, a corpus of scientific articles has been selected that have as object of study the press of Spain and that have been published in the period of the last five years (2014-2019). The methodology, with a quantitative and statistical basis, involved analyzing a number of different variables such as the subject matter of the selected newspapers, the geographical scope of the newspapers' circulation, the consumption of these media (print and online format), and the researchers' justification for the selection of the newspapers. The results reveal a bias in the scientific literature towards newspapers of national scope, with national titles featuring more prominently than regional ones. Even though the national press has a lower audience than the regional one. It can also be observed that scientific articles take a traditional view of the press, framed within a series of ideological principles, which we could label the "newsagents' effect".

RESUMEN

La prensa española ha sido objeto de numerosos trabajos científicos recientes. Pero ¿qué entiende la comunidad científica por prensa española? La presente investigación tiene como objetivo principal analizar cómo la comunidad de investigadores del ámbito de la Comunicación ha definido por extensión la noción del dominio «prensa española» en la literatura científica. Para ello, se ha seleccionado un corpus de artículos científicos que tengan como objeto de estudio a la prensa de España y que hayan sido publicados en el periodo de los últimos cinco años (2014-2019). Para alcanzar los objetivos propuestos en el presente estudio, se ha planteado una metodología con base cuantitativa y estadística que analiza diferentes variables como la temática de los periódicos escogidos, el ámbito geográfico de difusión, el consumo de dichos medios (en formato impreso como online) y la justificación de la elección por parte de los investigadores. Los resultados del estudio han demostrado la existencia de un sesgo de centralidad en la literatura científica, puesto que se ha otorgado un mayor protagonismo a los diarios nacionales que a los de ámbito regional. Aún cuando la prensa nacional posee una audiencia inferior a la regional. Asimismo, se ha observado que en los artículos científicos se tiene una visión tradicional de la prensa, enmarcada en una serie de principios ideológicos que podríamos denominar como «efecto kiosko».

KEYWORDS

media, press, journalism, media system, audience, media consumption

PALABRAS CLAVE / KEYWORDS

medios de comunicación, prensa, periodismo, sistema de medios, audiencia, consumo de medios
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1. Introduction

The communication media act as intermediaries between social reality and the viewer (Gomis-Sanahuja, 1974, pp. 530-531). By fulfilling this task, the media play a decisive role in the modern world: they bear the primary responsibility for providing citizens with information (Charaudeau, 2013, p. 39), especially about what is happening in society and in their surroundings (Wahl-Jorgensen and Hanitzsch, 2009, p. 3). The media are considered industries that create information for consumption by the public (De-Mateo, 1989, p. 211). Their control over the information agenda puts the media in a prominent position, making them the main source through which the public can find out what is going on in the world (Walgrave et al., 2017, p. 1). The consolidation of the information society towards the end of the twentieth century and the understanding of information as something intrinsic to society that goes beyond the human communication process (Mayoral, 2013, p. 37) has endowed the media with a critical role to play in the power-building process (Tubella-Casadevall & Alberich-Pascual, 2012, p. 99). The press holds a key position in the media landscape thanks to its long history, the wide range of issues it covers in its pages (Author, 2018) and its status as a social and political actor (Kircher, 2005, p. 115), making the newspaper an object of influence for actors in the communication process. For the reader, the press provides a better understanding and offers greater credibility than other media (Fernández-Gil, 2010, p. 136). The press has to relate and discuss political, social, economic and cultural news for a mass audience (Borrat, 1989, p. 67). In doing so, it fulfils a dual function. On the one hand, it has to meet society's information needs by covering current news events (Gomis-Sanahuja, 2008, p. 25) and, on the other hand, uphold ideological pluralism and contribute to the formation of public opinion (Kircher, 2005, p. 116) through the publication of opinion pieces (Author, 2020). In recent decades, the area of Communication has aroused great interest in the scientific field (Repiso et al., 2020, p. 2) and there have been many works that have addressed different aspects of this area of knowledge (e.g.: Castillo-Esparcia & Carretón-Ballester, 2010, Repiso & Torres-Salinas, 2014, Roses-Campos & Humanes-Humanes, 2018, Lozano-Ascencio et al., 2020, among others). Among the research in Communication, the press occupies a prominent place, representing about 20% of scientific production (Gómez-Escalonilla, 2020, p. 46). In addition, many authors have taken it as an object of study for works of various kinds thanks to its media relevance (e.g., Navarro-Beltrá & Martín-Llaguno, 2013, López-Pérez & Olvera-Lobo, 2015; García-Santamaría et al., 2016; Vizcaíno-Lagorda & Jiménez-Ruesta, 2018, among others). However, the study of the press presents a number of difficulties, since the theoretical concept of the press has to be translated into a practical domain, specifically describing it with a view to its analysis. Thus, the empirical definition of the press should not be the same in all studies: each paper should set out different criteria tailored to the specific objectives of the research in question. We believe that the related studies tend not to do this; accordingly, the main objective of this study is to conduct a detailed analysis of how the research community in the field of Communication has defined the notion of "the Spanish press" in their publications. To that end, we raise a series of questions: (a) Which media are used in the publications? (b) Are any selection criteria applied or is the choice completely arbitrary? (c) If selection criteria are applied, are they explicit or implicit criteria? (d) What are the most commonly analyzed types of newspaper in terms of subject matter and geographical area? (e) Does the frequency with which they appear in the studies correspond to audience measurement data? (f) Has the perception of the press in the university in Communication evolved or is it still similar to the first times? We believe that these are an interesting set of questions to ask when it is 50 years since the introduction of Communication university studies in Spain. This study is part of a wider doctoral research project focused on the study and analysis of the Spanish press. As such, the research presented here is considered a preliminary phase in the design and selection of the methodology to build the corpus that will subsequently be analyzed in the doctoral thesis.

2. Material and methods

To achieve the objectives set out above, a specific corpus was compiled, consisting of a selection of 87 research articles focusing on the Spanish press. The main multidisciplinary scientific databases were used to identify the articles; namely, Web of Science (Clarivate), Google Scholar (Alphabet), Scopus (Elsevier) and Dialnet (University of La Rioja and Dialnet Foundation). We selected all the articles focusing on the domain of the Spanish press, published between 2014 and 2019. Two data sets were then created. The first listed all the newspapers included in the articles selected for the study, presented by frequency of occurrence and then described in terms of certain characteristics. They were first classified in relation to their subject matter and geographical scope: 1. National General (NatGen), general-interest newspapers whose geographical coverage is national in scope; 2. Regional General (RegGen), general-interest newspapers with regional or local coverage; 3. National Economics (NatEco), business newspapers with national distribution; 4. National Sports (NatSpo), nationally-distributed sports newspapers. 5. National Religious (NatRel), newspapers with a

religious subject matter, regardless of the specific denomination, distributed across the entire country. Second, the newspapers were divided according to the publication format: print and online. Bearing in mind that some newspapers are available in both formats, we classified the newspapers with both print and digital versions in the category 'print', while the newspapers that only release an electronic version were categorized as 'online'. Third, audience and consumption data for these newspapers were also included, for both print and online formats. To that end, data were sourced from the General Media Study (EGM by its initials in Spanish), published by the Association for Media Research (AIMC)¹, and aimed at the analysis, measurement, and certification of audiences. The EGM analyzes media consumption in Spain through five studies: Press, Radio, TV, Magazines, and Multimedia. To that end, three types of methods are used: namely, personal interviews, telephone interviews and online interviews (totaling more than 150,000 interviews annually). The results are published three times a year. It should be noted that it was not possible to obtain data on all the newspapers in the present study, since the EGM report only provides information on a limited number of media sources. In addition, we used reports from comScore², a media measurement company that monitors audiences, brands and the behavior of consumers who view digital content. To do so, comScore presents two types of studies: Offline, measuring audiences for traditional media; and Online, measuring audiences on websites. The advantage of comScore is that in addition to sample data, it provides census-based data. Unified Digital Measurement (UDM) is a hybrid measurement method which records all website visitors and helps users to understand the size and quality of their audience. The second data set contained a table with the title of the scientific articles, the newspapers used in those articles, and the justification for selecting the newspapers in question. For the subsequent analysis, the studies were then categorized according to the type of criteria used in the selection of newspapers. To that end, three main characteristics were established: 1. Justification based on quantifiable data (JD), which can also be labeled a *hard criterion*. It refers to the articles that based the selection of newspapers on objective, quantifiable data, primarily drawn from sources of audience measurement information (e.g., EGM, OJD, comScore, etc.). 2. Arbitrary justification (AJ), which can also be labeled a *soft criterion*. It refers to studies that selected newspapers according to arbitrary criteria, mainly based on *a priori* assessments made by the authors themselves, and which cannot be objectively quantified. 3. No justification (NO), or a lack of criteria. This indicates articles that did not present any type of selection criteria (hard or soft) for the inclusion of newspapers. Similarly, the first characteristic—Justification based on quantifiable data (JD)—was broken down into four sub-characteristics referring to the type of data underpinning the justification: data sourced from the General Media Study (EGM); data sourced from the *Oficina de Justificación de la Difusión* (OJD); data sourced from a combination of the two previous reports (E-O); data sourced from other types of reports and rankings (RK); and lastly, data on circulation or consumption where the source is not indicated (NS).

3. Results y discussion

After processing the 87 scientific articles compiled, we identified the presence of 55 different names of newspapers used in these studies, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Frequency of occurrence of newspapers in scientific studies. Source: By the authors.

It should be highlighted that the newspaper that has most often been used as a focus of study is *El País* (83), followed at some distance by *El Mundo* (67) and *ABC* (58). Coming next are *La Vanguardia* (34), *El Periódico* (19) and *La Razón* (18). The latter newspaper is followed by a rather large gap, with far fewer occurrences registered for newspapers such as *El Correo* (6) and *Público* (6). Then, there is a substantial number of newspapers that register a single occurrence. This significant difference was to be expected, given that the newspapers that register more frequent occurrences are national general-interest papers and are therefore presumed to have wider circulation and higher readership throughout the country, as indicated by EGM data.

Figure 2. Classification of newspapers according to their subject matter and frequency of occurrence in scientific studies. Source: By the authors.

Figure 2 shows a *treemap* chart with the newspapers grouped by frequency and subject matter. The figure reveals a preponderance of general-interest newspapers—48 in total, with 347 occurrences in the different scientific articles. These data stand in contrast to those on the specialist newspapers, which only account for 7 newspaper titles and 15 occurrences in total: 4 sports newspapers (*Marca*, *AS*, *Mundo Deportivo* and *Sport*) with 4 occurrences; 2 business-related papers (*Expansión* and *Cinco Días*) with 10 occurrences; and, finally, one religious newspaper (*IslamHoy*) with a single occurrence. Researchers clearly show greater interest in the general-interest press. Figure 3 shows the area of influence of each newspaper.

Figure 3. Classification of newspapers according to their geographical area and frequency of occurrence in scientific studies. Source: By the authors.

While there is a larger number of regional newspaper titles—29 in total—they only register 47 occurrences in the research articles. Conversely, a smaller number of newspapers with nationwide circulation (only 26, including the specialist newspapers) account for 315 occurrences in the scientific articles. Of these, the top six alone register 279 occurrences. This result is of note because although communication research is not limited to Madrid and Barcelona, the presence of the regional press is marginal to say the least. Researchers lean towards newspapers of national scope, rather than seeking out more local titles. This may be an indication that research on the press does not usually connect with local actors and instead too often turns to the half-dozen national newspapers, probably reflecting the authors' *a priori* judgements. If we combine the characteristics analyzed above (subject matter and geographical coverage), the bias towards these six dominant newspapers can be seen more clearly (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Classification of newspapers according to their subject matter, geographical area, and frequency of occurrence in scientific studies. Source: By the authors.

When we talk about national newspapers, we are not referring exclusively to those published in Madrid. There are some newspapers that are not from Madrid but do have a national scope, as is the case with the Basque and Catalan titles: *La Vanguardia*, *El Periódico de Cataluña* or *El Correo del Pueblo Vasco*, for example. Furthermore, it should be borne in mind that much of the regional or local press belong to the same national media group; therefore, although there is a very diverse range of regional titles, they share the same national and international information. This is what happens in the case of groups such as Vocento, in which most of their regional newspapers (e.g., *Ideal*, *Sur*, *Diario Montañés*, etc.) report a good deal of the same information (usually national and international news). Also meriting attention is the case of the specialized press (sports, economic and religious), which appears very infrequently in specific studies. Despite having nationwide geographical coverage, such newspapers have a much smaller presence than the general-interest press, perhaps because their subject matter is limited to very specific issues that tend not to attract authors specializing in this area of study.

Figure 5. Classification of newspapers according to their format and frequency of occurrence in scientific studies. Source: By the authors.

Figure 5 shows a *treemap* chart organized by formats. We observe an overwhelming presence of newspapers that have a print and an online format: a total of 42 newspapers and a frequency of 346 occurrences. In comparison, there are 13 exclusively digital newspapers, with a frequency of only 16 occurrences. In light of these data, it is striking that even though these are recent studies—all from the last five years—there is not a greater presence of digital newspapers, as we address below. It is also noteworthy how some articles studying the internet coverage of certain news events still justify the selection of newspapers on the basis of circulation data for the paper version and not the consumption of such media online. It is also important to note in this section that the newspaper *Público*, although currently an online newspaper, did have a print edition until 2012. In this case, it has been counted as a print newspaper, since the studies in which it appears work with the physical version. Figure 6 is a scatter plot with the number of occurrences in communication studies on the horizontal axis and the EGM consumption metric for print materials on the vertical axis. National newspapers are marked in blue and regional ones in yellow.

Figure 6. Occurrences vs. EGM for print/comScore. Fuente: Elaboración propia.

As can be seen, the variables are moderately correlated ($R^2=0.8$). The points fall roughly on an imaginary line between *El País* and the origin. Those newspapers that lie above this line are underrepresented in the studies (relative to their readership) whereas those that are below are overrepresented. The position of *ABC* is salient in that it is probably the most clearly overrepresented newspaper in the scientific literature. The same is true, albeit to a lesser extent, of *El Mundo* and *La Razón*. Quite the opposite is observed with *20 Minutos*: despite being the third-ranked Spanish newspaper in terms of readership, it has rarely been included in academic studies. One might imagine that this is due to the fact that it is a free newspaper. Even more striking is the case of *La Voz de Galicia* because it is the regional paper with the highest audience impact and is one of the top five nationally. However, as mentioned above, it is a prestigious regional newspaper that does not seem to have caught the attention of researchers, who give more weight to nationwide newspapers with smaller circulations. However, if we construct the same type of graph with online audience measurement data, the results differ notably. The audience data have been taken from the monthly averages over the last year provided by the well-known media measurement and analytics company, comScore. They have been extracted from successive monthly top tens and can be found published by the media sources themselves; as such, not all the newspapers are included here, just the most prominent ones. The first thing that can be seen is a lower correlation than before (in this case $R^2=0.5$). If we draw an imaginary line between *El País* and the origin we can see that most of the newspapers are underrepresented in the research. This is especially evident in the case of *La Vanguardia* (the online paper with the largest audience), but it is also clear for *ABC* and *El Mundo*. The overrepresentation of *ABC* noted in the previous context is no longer applicable in the online context. The position of *20 Minutos* is similar to that of the print version, but two exclusively online news sources make a strong appearance alongside it: *El Español* and *El Confidencial*. These seven online news sources currently constitute the basic core of the Spanish press when considered in terms of online audience measurement data. These are websites with monthly audiences that reach and even exceed 20 million users. Any study seeking to analyze the journalistic discourse that reaches the average Spanish reader should consider all of them. In the range of 10 to 14 million, we find a second group of four titles: two online (*El Diario* and *Huffington Post*) and two mixed (*El Periódico* and *La Razón*). As expected, the online ones appear to the left (little impact on research) and the others more to the right (greater impact). Below these are *Público* and, once again, *La Voz de Galicia*, which is the only regional title with a large online audience, thus underscoring our comments referring to the previous graph. *OkDiario* features in the comScore rankings, a news source with an audience of between 12 and 14 million monthly users; interestingly, however, it was not selected by any of the research papers. The total lack of attention in this case is just as striking as the underrepresentation of the other examples cited above. It would appear to be a clear indication that the criterion for selection and analysis employed by the authors in the specialized literature bears little relation to the audience changes that the media are undergoing in their transition from print to online; on the contrary, the research appears anchored in certain models of the print press that date back several decades. Lastly, we have analyzed the justification

the authors provide for the selection of newspapers in their studies. To do so, we rely on the characteristics explained above in the Material and Methods section. Only 21 articles were found to have employed a hard selection criterion (based on data). Of those, it can be seen that 7 rely on data obtained from the EGM, while 10 draw on the OJD. In two articles, the authors decided to establish selection criteria that combine data from both reports. There is a single article that uses another ranking (AEDE, the Spanish Newspaper Publishers' Association) and one that does not state the source from which it has obtained the data. As suggested above, none of the articles use comScore data. Indeed, we note that in this group of articles there is a tendency to use two classic reference reports, EGM and OJD, above other types of reports on media consumption and marketing (such as comScore) that are becoming more prevalent in the current market. While the selection may be based on a hard criterion in a few cases, those studies rely solely on one specific element. An example is the article by Author (2015) in which the newspapers *El País*, *Marca*, *El Correo* and *El Mundo* are selected because they are the only ones that have a specific data journalism section on their websites. In this case, although they still do not base their selection on consumption or circulation, they do set objective criteria. In contrast, there are twice as many articles that present a soft criterion—a total of 42. In this group, two main trends are observed. The first, clearly ideological in nature, is classifying newspapers according to their political leaning, without providing any data or specific rationale to support this classification. We thus observe a general tendency to define *El País* as a left-leaning or center-left newspaper, *El Mundo* as a right-wing newspaper that leans liberal on economic issues, and *ABC* and *La Razón* as conservative, Catholic, pro-monarchy newspapers. Even if these categories are accurate and still applicable, it has become very clear that said newspapers are not the only actors in the Spanish press; as such, using only these titles in an attempt to entirely cover "the ideological spectrum" impoverishes the research framework. It would seem that the authors are trying to "lay the groundwork" to ensure that their results readily fit their *a priori* judgements that motivated the research itself. If so, the four abovementioned newspapers are perfectly suited to the task. However, the inclusion of new online media with a large audience and without a biased political profile, as may be the case with *El Confidencial*, is not as appealing because it is certain to yield results that are less black-and-white and more complex to analyze. The second trend is to treat a newspaper as prestigious and important without relying on any type of data or prior analysis to support the decision. We thus see articles in which the selection of national and regional newspapers is simply justified by a mention of their relevance and prestige. Perhaps the underlying issue here is researchers' fear of failing to include the media that "ought to always be included" in such an analysis, with a mind to the reviewers who are going to evaluate their work rather than the real audiences that should be studied. Likewise, in one of the articles analyzed we observed that the authors combine the two previous categories; that is, they rely on data from media reports to propose the newspapers, but then choose them according to personal criteria. As such, this is once again a soft criterion, since it is based on a personal choice, or what we would refer to as a *mental framework*. Lastly, we found a total of 24 articles in which no justification is given for the selection of newspapers; that is, there is either no criterion or it is not revealed. The articles simply state the name of the newspapers but offer no explanation as to why they have been selected. Therefore, we argue that the newspapers have been cherry-picked in the sense that the selection is based on personal interests that cannot be generalized in a clear criterion. This type of selection can exert a notable influence on the results obtained.

4. Conclusions

Based on the results obtained, we can answer the questions raised at the beginning of this study and gain an understanding of how the press has been conceived of in recent communication research. These results show that the researchers have an image of the Spanish press based on a series of postulates, which sometimes differ from the journalistic reality of our country. This image seems to have evolved little in the 50 years of university studies in communication in Spain and seems anchored in the mid-1980s and early 1990s. The results also point to a bias in the scientific literature towards newspapers of national scope, as they have been given greater prominence than regional ones, even when the latter are well positioned in circulation and consumption reports. The most extreme case in this regard is that of *La Voz de Galicia*, which despite being a regional newspaper, is among the top five general-interest titles in Spain, according to the EGM. These findings suggest that the lack of interest in this type of media may be due to researchers' concern that the scientific community will undervalue studies that exclusively analyze the regional press, prompting them to include national newspapers in their studies. Another explanation could be related to the funding of the research itself, since in many areas of Spain the regional funding that researchers can apply for is less than that available at the national level. These issues may result in researchers turning away from the regional press in favor of national newspapers, perpetuating the aforementioned bias in communication studies. All this despite the fact

that the university studies of Communication have grown to cover most of the country, by the hand of the administrative decentralization and the development of the competences of the regional governments. Furthermore, we believe that the academic world's view of the Spanish press is somewhat static as it is anchored in historical references that date back as far as the beginning of the transition to democracy. They thus effectively function as an echo chamber, reinforcing the ideological profiles they seek to find in their studies (for example, when speaking of newspapers that are left-leaning, right-wing, pro-monarchy, etc.). On the one hand, the static perspective of the press in academic research may be due to the ideological certainty provided by certain newspapers, especially those described as "right-wing", which are attributed certain ideological profiles. On the other hand, it could relate to "fear of innovation", that is, fear of including new titles outside the traditional core of the national general-interest printed press, such as regional media or digital newspapers. This situation can also be described as "fear of peer review", as it is sometimes referred to in academia. That is, researchers feel obliged to study certain newspapers that align with the scientific community's conception of the Spanish press. In this regard, the "newsagents' effect" is seen to exert a notable influence, which indicates that academia is finding it somewhat hard to gauge the reality demanded by the real audience when analyzing new media. It has also been observed that even when there is a hard criterion—in other words, an objective criterion based on data—it still tends to be outdated, with a justification based on traditional reports such as the EGM and OJD, whose data are more focused on the readership and circulation of print media. As noted in this study, new reports have burst onto the scene in the field of media and audience analysis, with comScore being one example. Despite being an important source of audience measurement data, the impact of these new reports is not being reflected in academic studies. At present, newspapers' websites represent an important source of media consumption by the audience; there are even some newspapers that only publish news online. Therefore, these digital platforms should be measured according to their traffic. We thus argue that Spanish communication research still has room for development when it comes to analyzing the online phenomenon in all its dimensions, with studies analyzing print versions of newspapers continuing to prevail. We therefore view this study as an initial approach to the issues surrounding the concept of the Spanish press in the scientific literature. The main contribution made by this article is that it provides communication researchers with an understanding of the empirical definition of the press in previous studies. It is also worth noting the innovative nature of the methodology, whereby an analysis of media consumption is conducted, but taking scientific articles as the focus of study. Moreover, there is the relevance of the data obtained, which has allowed us to gain an understanding of the behavior of researchers in the study of the Spanish press. In this regard, we believe that the methodology proposed in this study can provide a starting point for new studies seeking to analyze the press from an academic perspective. Similarly, it is our view that the results underscore the potential for future communication research focusing on the regional press as well as the digital press and the consumption of digital media, while turning attention to new newspaper titles and new audience measurement reports.

Notes

¹ Available at <[http:// www.aimc.es/](http://www.aimc.es/)> (last accessed on 23-09-2021).

² Available at <www.comscore.com/> (last accessed on 23-09-2021).

Supports

This study is part of a doctoral research project supported by an FPU (a university faculty training grant) from the Ministry of Education and Vocational Training, and the R+D Project. by the Spanish Ministry of Science Innovation and Universities under the framework R&D project RTI2018-098966-B-I00.

References

Borrat, H. (1989). El periódico, actor del sistema político. *Anàlisi*, 12, 67-80. <https://bit.ly/3u3a8LY>

Castillo-Esparcia, A., & Carretón-Ballester, M. C. (2010). Investigación en Comunicación. Estudio bibliométrico de las revistas de comunicación en España. *Communication & Society*, 23(2), 289-327. <https://revistas.unav.edu/index.php/communication-and-society/article/view/36234>

Charadeau, P. (2013). *El discurso de la información. La construcción del espejo social*. Barcelona: Gedisa Editorial.

De-Mateo, R. (1989). The Evolution of the Newspaper Industry in Spain, 1939-87. *European Journal of Communication*, 4(2), 211-226. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0267323189004002006>

- Fernández-Gil, J. R. (2010). Fuentes de análisis para el estudio de la prensa diaria. *Anales de Documentación*, 13, 135-158. <https://revistas.um.es/analesdoc/article/view/107101>
- García-Santamaría, J. V., Pérez-Serrano, M. J., & Maestro-Espínola, L. (2016). Los clubs de suscriptores como nuevo modelo de financiación de la prensa española. *El profesional de la información*, 25(3), 395-403. <https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2016.may.09>
- Gómez-Escalínilla, G. (2020) La investigación de la comunicación en España desde la Economía Política de la Comunicación. *IC – Revista Científica de Información y Comunicación*, 17, 31- 56. <https://doi.org/10.12795/ic.2020.i17.02>
- Gomis-Sanahuja, L. (1974). *El medio media: La función política de la prensa*. Madrid: Seminarios y Ediciones.
- Gomis-Sanahuja, L. (2008). *Teoría de los géneros periodísticos*. Barcelona: Editorial UOC.
- Kircher, M. (2005). La prensa escrita: actor social y político, espacio de producción cultural y fuente de información histórica. *Revista de Historia*, 10, 115-122. <http://170.210.83.53/index.php/historia/article/view/219>
- López-Pérez, L., & Olvera-Lobo, M. D. (2015). Tratamiento de la información científica en las ediciones digitales de los periódicos españoles. *El profesional de la información*, 24(6), 766-777. <https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2015.nov.08>
- Lozano-Ascencio, C., Gaitán-Moya, J. A., Caffarel-Serra, C., & Piñuel-Raigada, J. L. (2020). Una década de investigación universitaria sobre Comunicación en España, 2007-2018. *El Profesional de la información*, 29(4), 1-16. <https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2020.jul.12>
- Mayoral, J. (2013). *Redacción periodística. Medios, géneros y formatos*. Madrid: Editorial Síntesis.
- Navarro-Beltrán, M., & Martín-Llaguno, M. (2013). Análisis bibliométrico de la investigación sobre mujer y publicidad: diferencias en medios impresos y audiovisuales. *Comunicar*, 41(21), 105-114. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C41-2013-10>
- Repiso, R., Berlanga, I., Said-Hung, E., & Castillo-Esparcia, A. (2020). Titularidad y cátedras en Comunicación en España (2000-2019). Distribución, ritmos de promoción, transferencia entre universidades y endogamia. *El profesional de la información*, 29(4), 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2020.jul.22>
- Repiso, R., & Torres-Salinas, D. (2014). Comunicación y Documentación: dos disciplinas convergentes pero distintas. *Anuario ThinkEPI*, 8, 225-229. <https://thinkepi.profesionaldelainformacion.com/index.php/ThinkEPI/article/view/29585>
- Roses-Campos, S., & Humanes-Humanes, M. L. (2018). Conflictos en los roles profesionales de los periodistas en España: Ideales y práctica. *Comunicar*, 58(27), 65-74. <https://doi.org/10.3916/C58-2019-06>
- Tubella-Casadevall, I., & Alberich-Pascual, J. (2009). *Comprender los Media en la Sociedad de la Información*. Barcelona: Editorial UOC.
- Vizcaíno-Laorga, R., & Jiménez-Ruesta, J. (2018). Rediseño en la prensa impresa española del siglo XXI. *El profesional de la información*, 27(1), 124-135. <https://doi.org/10.3145/epi.2018.ene.12>
- Wahl-Jorgensen, K., & Hanitzsch, T. (2009). Introduction: On why and how we should do journalism studies". In K. Wahl-Jorgensen & T. Hanitzsch (Eds.), *The handbook of journalism studies* (pp. 3-16). New York: Routledge.
- Walgrave, S., Sevenans, J., Zoizner, A., & Ayling, M. (2017). The Media Independency of Political Elites. In P. Van-Aelst & S. Walgrave (Eds.), *How political actors use the media* (pp. 127-145). Cham: Palgrave Macmillan.